

Synthesis and characterization of UO_2^{VI} , Th^{IV} and VO^{IV} complexes with a Schiff base and their derivatives with monochloroacetic acid

Ranjan Kumar Mohapatra

Department of Chemistry, Orissa School of Mining Engineering (Degree Stream), Keonjhar-758 001, Orissa, India

E-mail : ranjank_mohapatra@yahoo.com

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Abstract : A series of UO_2^{VI} , Th^{IV} and VO^{IV} complexes have been synthesized with Schiff base "1,7-di(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)-2,3,5,6-tetraaza-1,6-heptadiene-4-thione" derived from thiocarbohydrazide and salicylaldehyde. Reaction of these complexes with monochloroacetic acid yielded another series of complexes having Schiff base "3-(1'-*o*-hydroxyphenyl-2'-azaethen-2'-yl)-2-(1'-*o*-hydroxyphenyl-2'-azaethen-2'-yl)imino-4-thiazolidinone" obtained after cyclization with monochloroacetic acid. The complexes are characterized on the basis of elemental analysis, thermal analysis, molar conductivity, magnetic moment, electronic, infrared spectral studies. The results indicate that the VO^{IV} ion is tetra coordinated yielding paramagnetic complexes, UO_2^{VI} ion is hexa coordinated where as Th^{IV} ion is octa coordinated yielding diamagnetic complexes of above stoichiometry. The ESR spectral data for VO^{IV} complexes and all ^1H NMR spectra for diamagnetic complexes are in consistent with the above results.

Keywords : Schiff base, template synthesis, structure and thermal properties, ESR, ^1H NMR spectra.

Introduction

In recent years extensive research in the chemistry of metal chelates involving chelating Schiff base containing nitrogen, oxygen and sulphur donors have steadily grown in many areas including synthesis, structure elucidation, reaction kinetics, redox behavior and biochemical reactions. The biological aspects of these complexes owing to their biopotency¹⁻⁴ have been the major cause of tremendous progress of research in this domain. Aromatic *o*-hydroxyaldehydes form stable complexes and the presence of a phenolic hydroxyl group at their *ortho*-position imparts an additional donor site in the molecule. Survey of literature reveals that the complexes of UO_2^{VI} , Th^{IV} and VO^{IV} ions with Schiff base ligand containing NOS donors, synthesized from thiocarbohydrazide and salicylaldehyde and their reactions with monochloroacetic acid have not been studied as yet, which prompted us to carry such type of investigation keeping in view of interesting stereo chemical possibilities, enhanced stabilities and their wide applications in the above mentioned fields. This is a part of the continuing investigation on the coordination chemistry of multidentate ligand containing NOS donors⁵⁻⁸.

Results and discussion

The complexes were formulated from the analytical data and molar conductance data support the suggested formulae (Table 1). The complexes are highly coloured and insoluble in water and common organic solvents such as ethanol, methanol, acetone, CCl_4 , CHCl_3 , benzene and ether but moderately soluble in highly coordinating solvents such as DMF and DMSO. They are highly stable under normal conditions and all of them decompose above 250 °C. The molar conductance data values in DMSO for the complexes indicate the complexes to be non-electrolyte in nature. However, the conductivity value is higher than as expected for non-electrolytes probably due to partial solvolysis of the complexes in DMSO medium⁹.

IR spectra :

As the Schiff base ligand could not be isolated, the spectra of the complexes were compared with spectra of the starting materials and other related compounds. The bands observed in the spectra of metal complexes at ~1450, ~1365, ~1040, ~740 cm^{-1} are assigned to thioimide I, II, III, IV bands respectively of TCH skeleton¹⁰. All the above bands appear nearly at the same

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the complexes

Sl. no.	Compd.	Colour	Yield (%)	μ_{eff}	Λ_m^a	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				
						C	H	N	S	M
1.	[UO ₂ (L)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Brocken white	75	Dia.	12.2	29.09 (29.12)	2.54 (2.58)	9.01 (9.06)	5.14 (5.17)	38.46 (38.51)
2.	[UO ₂ (L')(H ₂ O) ₂]	Reddish yellow	71	Dia.	10.3	30.96 (31.00)	2.40 (2.43)	8.45 (8.51)	4.83 (4.86)	36.12 (36.17)
3.	Th(L)(NO ₃) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	White haze	64	Dia.	21.5	25.53 (25.49)	2.25 (2.27)	11.89 (11.93)	4.51 (4.54)	32.91 (32.95)
4.	[Th(L')(NO ₃) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Light buff	62	Dia.	19.8	27.39 (27.42)	2.18 (2.15)	11.25 (11.29)	4.26 (4.30)	31.15 (31.18)
5.	[VO(L)].2H ₂ O	Black	77	1.73	11.6	43.34 (43.37)	3.81 (3.85)	13.46 (13.49)	7.72 (7.71)	12.24 (12.28)
6.	[VO(L')].2H ₂ O	Greenish black	74	1.76	9.2	44.79 (44.83)	3.48 (3.51)	12.27 (12.30)	6.99 (7.03)	11.14 (11.20)

^a $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$.

position as found in the free TCH implying non coordination of thioimide sulphur or nitrogen atom to the metal ion. The absence of band at $\sim 3350 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to phenolic $\nu(\text{O-H})$ and appearance of a band at $\sim 1500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ instead of 1280 cm^{-1} due to phenolic $\nu(\text{C-O})$ of salicylaldehyde moiety and appearance of another band at $\sim 1610 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ as comparatively lower frequency region than usual free $\nu(\text{C=N})$ ^{11,12} lead us to suggest that phenolic oxygen atom after deprotonation and azomethine nitrogen atom has taken part in complexation as evidenced from the appearance of bands in the region $530\text{--}515 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $460\text{--}440 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to $\nu(\text{M-O})$ and $\nu(\text{M-N})$ respectively¹³. For the complexes (2), (4), (6) the band due to $\nu(\text{C=S})$ was found to be absent and new bands are observed at $\sim 1680 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to $\nu(\text{C=O})$ and at the region $\sim 750\text{--}800 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to $\nu(\text{C-S})$ stretching vibration indicating the formation of thiazolidinone ring which was further confirmed by the appearance of another band at $\sim 1630 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for $\nu(\text{C=N})$. The uranyl complexes exhibit a strong band at $\sim 940\text{--}900 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the medium intensity band at $\sim 835\text{--}820 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{O=U=O})$ and $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{O=U=O})$ mode respectively¹⁴. The band at 1024 cm^{-1} is assigned to the ν_2 mode of the NO₃ group. The bands at 1480 and 1380 cm^{-1} are the two split bands ν_4 and ν_1 respectively, of the coordinated nitrate ion¹⁵. The magnitude of $\Delta\nu = (\nu_4 - \nu_1) = 100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ shows the unidentate coordination of the nitrate ion¹⁵. In the oxovanadium polychelates strong bands at $\sim 965 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned to $\nu(\text{V=O})$ modes¹⁶. However, these bands are absent in the complexes of Th^{IV}. Besides, the additional bands observed at $\sim 3500(\text{s})$, $\sim 1600(\text{s})$ and $\sim 880 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the com-

plexes may be assigned to $\nu(\text{O-H})$, $\delta(\text{O-H})$ and $\rho(r)$ of coordinated or lattice water, which is further confirmed by thermal analysis. However all the complexes except (5) and (6) lose water when heated to $\sim 140 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ indicating the presence of coordinated water molecules whereas complexes (5) and (6) at $\sim 70\text{--}100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ due to lattice water.

Thermal analysis :

The thermogram of the complexes exhibited the characteristics of coordinated water as well as water of crystallization. In VO^{IV} complexes weight loss was encountered at $\sim 70 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ with a broad endothermic peak at the same temperature corresponding to two molecules of water of crystallization¹⁷. For other complexes, the elimination of coordinated water occurred in single step as supported by an exothermic peak at $\sim 145 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Simultaneous elimination of coordinated water suggests them to be in the same chemical environment¹⁸. The anhydrous complexes remain stable up to $\sim 340\text{--}440 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and there after the complexes show rapid degradation presumably due to decomposition of organic constituents of the complex molecules as indicated by the steep fall in the percentage weight loss. The decomposition continues up to $\sim 700 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and reached to a stable product in each complex as indicated by the consistency in weight in the plateau of the thermogram. This corresponds to the composition to their stable oxides. The decomposition temperature varies for different complexes as shown in Table 2. The thermal stability of such complexes is found to be in the following order.

Table 2. Thermal characteristics of the complexes

Complex	Total wt. for T_g (mg)	Temp. range of water loss ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	% wt. of water loss Found (Calcd.)	Decomposition temp. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	% wt. of residue Found (Calcd.)	Composition of the residue
1	103	140-195	5.77 (5.82)	410-700	45.37 (45.41)	U_3O_8
2	109	140-200	5.41 (5.47)	390-690	42.62 (42.65)	U_3O_8
3	105	145-200	5.07 (5.11)	420-690	37.36 (37.39)	ThO_2
4	97	143-210	4.78 (4.83)	380-680	35.34 (35.38)	ThO_2
5	87	70-100	8.62 (8.67)	390-660	43.81 (43.85)	V_2O_5
6	95	75-95	7.87 (7.91)	380-660	39.95 (40.00)	V_2O_5

(L) Complexes : $\text{Th}^{\text{IV}} > \text{UO}_2^{\text{VI}} > \text{VO}^{\text{IV}}$

(L') Complexes : $\text{UO}_2^{\text{VI}} > \text{Th}^{\text{IV}} > \text{VO}^{\text{IV}}$

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectra of the UO_2^{VI} complexes are quite similar. The complexes display mainly one weak band at ~ 440 nm and a highly intense band at ~ 280 nm, which may be due to $^1\Sigma_g^+ \rightarrow ^3\Pi_u$ transitions and charge transfer transitions respectively¹⁹. It may be noted that the band occurring at ~ 360 nm is due to uranyl moiety because of apical oxygen $\rightarrow f^0(u)$ transition²⁰ is being merged with the ligand band due to $n \rightarrow \Pi^*$ transition as evident from broadness and intensity. The electronic spectra of Th^{IV} exhibit only one extra highly intensive band in the region 340-350 nm which may be due to charge transfer band besides the ligand bands. However the electronic spectra could not provide structural details of these complexes. The electronic spectra of VO^{IV} complexes show three bands at ~ 813 , ~ 568 and ~ 431 nm which correspond to transitions, $2B_2 \rightarrow 2E$, $2B_2 \rightarrow 2B_1$ and $2B_1 \rightarrow 2A_1$ respectively, indicating the complexes to be penta coordinated and having square-pyramidal geometry, which is further confirmed by their ESR spectral data's.

^1H NMR spectra :

The ^1H NMR spectrum of the diamagnetic complexes in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ show the azomethane protons at δ 8.4 ppm. The disappearance of the signal due to the phenolic OH protons and the downfield shift of the signal due to the azomethane protons in the corresponding complexes, indicate the coordination of the phenolic oxygen and azomethane nitrogen to the metal ion²¹. On the other hand all the complexes show a complex broad multiplet in the region δ 6.51-7.73 ppm corresponding to eight aromatic protons. In case of the complexes (1) and (3), the signals due to $-\text{NH}-\text{N}=\text{}$ protons appear at δ 9.3 ppm, where as for other complexes this signal is not observed. This suggests the formation of thiozolidinone ring, which is also conformed from the IR spectra of the complexes.

An additional peak is also observed in case of the complexes (2) and (4) for CH_2 protons (thiozolidinone ring) at δ 3.42 ppm (singlet). Besides, an additional peak at δ 3.6 ppm is observed in all the complexes indicating the presence of coordinated water²².

The representative spectrum of $[\text{UO}_2(\text{L}')(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ complex is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. ^1H NMR spectrum of $[\text{UO}_2(\text{L}')(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$.

ESR spectra :

The ESR spectra of VO^{IV} complexes, recorded in DMSO solution at 300 K, show a typical eight lines pattern which indicate that a single vanadium is present in the molecule, i.e. it is a monomer. The magnetic and bonding parameters deduced from the spectra are shown in Table 3. The covalency parameter α^2 as calculated from g_{\parallel} , g_{\perp} and A_{\parallel} values was found to be ~ 0.50 . The

Table 3. ESR spectral data of VO^{IV} complexes

Complexes	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	g_{av}	A_{\parallel}	A_{\perp}	A_{av}	α^2
5	1.97	1.99	1.98	175	74	107.67	0.49
6	1.97	1.99	1.98	178	76	110	0.50

observed data show that g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} values are closer to 2 and $g_{\perp} > g_{\parallel}$, indicates that the unpaired electron is present in the d_{xy} orbital with square-pyramidal geometry around the VO^{IV} chelate^{23,24}.

Materials and methods :

The chemicals used were of AR grade. The solvents were purified before use by standard procedures. Thiocarbohydrazide was synthesized according to literature method of Audrieth *et al.*²⁵. As the Schiff base ligand isolation proved futile, all the metal complexes were synthesized *in situ* by taking different amount of metal salts, thiocarbohydrazide and salicylaldehyde.

Preparation of the complexes (1), (3) and (5) :

An ethanolic solution of hydrated metal nitrates/vanadyl sulphate (1 mmol) was added to a hot ethanolic solution of the mixture of thiocarbohydrazide (1 mmol) and salicylaldehyde (2 mmol). The resulting mixture was refluxed on water bath for 4–5 h during which a coloured complex was precipitated out in each case. It was filtered off, washed several times with ethanol followed by ether and finally dried *in vacuo* over anhydrous CaCl₂.

Preparation of the complexes (2), (4) and (6) :

The ethanolic suspension of the above complexes were treated with monochloroacetic acid in 1 : 1 molar ratio. Again the mixtures were refluxed for 3–4 h on a water bath during which different coloured metal complexes were precipitated out (Table 1). The progress of the reaction was signalled by colour change of the resulting solution. It was filtered off, washed several times with ethanol fol-

lowed by ether and finally dried *in vacuo* over anhydrous CaCl₂.

Determination of uranium, thorium and vanadium was done by standard methods²⁶. Sulphur was estimated as BaSO₄.

Room temperature magnetic susceptibilities were measured by Gouy method²⁷. The molar conductance measurements were carried out at room temperature with a Toshniwal conductivity Bridge (Model CL-01-06, cell constant 0.5 cm⁻¹) using 1 × 10⁻³ M solution of the complexes in DMSO. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen contents of the complexes were estimated by using a MLW-CHN microanalyser. FTIR spectra in KBr pellets were recorded on a Varian FTIR spectrophotometer, Australia. The electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer* spectrophotometer. Thermo gravimetric analysis was done by Netzch-429 thermoanalyser. The ¹H NMR spectra of the complexes were recorded in DMSO-*d*₆ medium on Jeol GSX-400 model equipment. The ESR spectrum of the complex has only been recorded in solid state on Varian Associate spectrophotometer using 100 KHz, X-band (RT), scan range 2.0 × 1 KG and field set 3200.

Based on the foregoing observations the following tentative structures have been proposed for the present complexes.

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